

The Impact of the Organizational Climate in Enhancing Creative Behavior

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify the impact of organizational climate on workers creative behavior at Jordanian pharmaceutical industry, through the identification of trends in the study sample of organizational climate dimensions, and workers creative behavior. And to identify the possibility of the existence of a statistical significant difference in their attitudes as it relates to organizational climate, which can be attributed to the variables of gender, age, academic qualification, experience, and job level. To achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher developed a questionnaire for the detection of the dimensions of (responsibility, team commitment, rewards, flexibility, and goal clarity) and workers creative behavior. To achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher developed a questionnaire for exploring organizational climate dimensions (flexibility, responsibility, goals clarity, team commitment and rewards) and the level of workers creative behavior. The study sample consisted of (445) employees and managers in pharmaceutical industrial organizations. Sample was selected randomly, and in light of this, data was collected and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

The research most important findings and conclusions are:

- 1- The arithmetic mean of the estimates of workers in the pharmaceutical industrial organizations towards organizational climate dimensions and workers creative behavior were moderate.*
- 2- The arithmetic mean of the estimates of workers towards organizational climate dimensions were moderate, and on the following order of importance (responsibility, team commitment, rewards, flexibility, and goal clarity).*
- 3- There is a statistically significant impact of organizational climate dimensions in employees creative behavior at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in pharmaceutical industrial organizations.*
- 4- There were no statistical significant differences between the estimates averages of members of study sample on organizational climate the due to variables (gender, age, academic qualification, experience, and job level.).*

Keywords: Organizational climate, Creative behavior, Pharmaceutical industry organizations

1.1 Introduction

Over the past two decades globalization, technological progress, short product life cycles and increased competition imposed new challenges to business organizations, in order to cope with these changes and maintain competitive advantage organizations need to innovate in products, technologies and management practices. Organizations that want to achieve success and excellence in performance must encourage its employees to offer new ideas, through providing a positive organizational climate that supports creative behavior (Solomon et al., 2004).

Organizational climate is one of the main determinants of the ability of organizations to achieve their goals; because of its a profound influence in the formation of employees perceptions, and their creative behavior, also in building the organization's ability to use its resources effectively.

Pharmaceutical sector plays an important role in supporting Jordanian economy, where drugs are exported to more than 60 countries around the world. Also, it contributes to the economic development and increases national income, through the generation of innovations, market development, job creation, and the introduction of advanced technology.

1.2 Importance of the Study

the significance of the current study can determine as follows:

Scientific importance

- This study linked between new Organizational climate dimensions that haven't been linked by Arabic previous studies, such as clarity of organizational goals, flexibility, and commitment of teamwork. It is also the first study that apply to the pharmaceutical manufacturing sector in Jordan.
- This study provides experimental evidence to the scientific community about the relationship between Organizational climate and creative behavior.

Practical importance

- It is expected that the results of this study will benefit the decision-makers in the pharmaceutical industry to clarify the impact of Organizational climate on employees creative behavior.
- Results of this study will benefit the pharmaceutical industry to improve the Organizational climate dimensions which increases the profitability and effectiveness of their organizations.
- This study will also contribute through the recommendations to be submitted for strengthening positive the Organizational climate and creative behavior among workers because of its effective impact in the face of challenges.

1.3 Study objectives

The study seeks to achieve a main aim, which is related to exploring the effect of organizational climate dimensions on creative employee behavior. Based on that main aim, this study aims at identifying:

- The level of organizational climate, and the level of employee creative behavior in Jordanian pharmaceutical companies from the perspective of the sample members.

- The impact of organizational climate on employee creative behavior in Jordanian pharmaceutical companies from the perspective of the sample members.
- The impact of organizational climate dimensions on employee creative behavior in Jordanian pharmaceutical companies from the perspective of the sample members.

1.4 Problem and Questions of the Study

The problem of the study can be stated in the following question:

What is the effect of Organizational climate in pharmaceutical manufacturing on employees creative behavior?. From this question, the following sub questions are derived

- What is the level of Organizational climate, Organizational climate dimensions (responsibility, team commitment rewards, flexibility, and goal clarity) in the pharmaceutical industry?.
- What is the level of employees creative behavior in the pharmaceutical industry?.
- What is the effect of Organizational climate dimensions in pharmaceutical manufacturing on employees creative behavior?.
- Are there statistical significant differences between the averages of estimates of the study sample toward organizational climate due to the variables (gender, age, educational qualification, years of experience, and job title)?

1.5 The study model

Fig. 1: the study model

1.6 Study Hypothesis

Based on the model of the study, the following hypotheses were developed:

- **The first main hypothesis** : there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for Organizational climate on employees creative behavior.
- **The Second main hypothesis** : there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for Organizational climate dimensions (flexibility, responsibility, rewards, clarity and team commitment) on employees creative behavior.

Sub hypothesis1: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for flexibility on employees creative behavior.

Sub hypothesis2: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for responsibility on employees creative behavior.

Sub hypothesis3: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for rewards on employees creative behavior.

Sub hypothesis4: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for clarity on employees creative behavior.

Sub hypothesis5: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for team commitment on employees creative behavior.

- **The Third main hypothesis** : there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of demographic factors (gender, age, educational level, experience, job title) organizational climate.

- **Sub hypothesis1:** there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of gender on workers perception towards organizational climate.

Sub hypothesis2: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of age on workers perception towards organizational climate.

Sub hypothesis3: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of educational level on workers perception towards organizational climate.

Sub hypothesis4: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of experience on workers perception towards organizational climate.

Sub hypothesis5: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of job title on workers perception towards organizational climate.

2. Literature review

2.1 Organizational climate concept

The historical origin of organizational climate concept was launched in ideas of human relations school, which stressed the importance of social and psychological factors in individuals productivity. Kurt Lewin presented the concept of organizational

climate in (1939), and in 1960s interest began in studying this topic at organizational behavior and organization theory field. Organizational climate can be defined as a common understanding of organization members about the characteristics of the work environment, practices, policies, procedures and incentive systems in the organization (Bowen. & Ostroff, 2004). Organizational climate was defined also as individual perceptions about organizational settings such as decision-making, leadership type, and job tasks (Banoura, 2014).

Organizational climate has a great importance because of its direct impact in the organizational processes, functions, effectiveness, and its relationship with the surrounding external environment. In fact, recent studies have considered organizational climate as organizational phenomenon that affect job satisfaction of employees and their performance, which affects the success of the organization. Organizational culture and organizational climate dimensions interact with each others to influence employees behavior, also healthy organizational climate creates a favorable environment for innovation through the cooperation of workers to find new ways to accomplish tasks (Francisco et al., 2004).

The presence of a healthy organizational climate is a catalyst for the adoption of creative behavior, healthy organizational climate provide flexibility and autonomy in selection of ideas, and give the creative staff more freedom in communications and overcome formalization and routine. But unhealthy organizational climate based on the inertia and lack of flexibility does not encourage creativity, and does not help the creators to offer any new ideas (Alzobi & Alazeb, 2007). The importance of identifying nature of prevailing organizational climate in any organization aims to adopt policies that promote the positive aspects and correct the negative aspects, as well as improve the mental health of workers and their commitment, which satisfy the needs and desires of individuals (Atheer, 2012).

2.2 Organizational climate dimensions

Many researchers tried to determine dimensions of organizational climate, Its also noted that there is a differences between researchers to quality and number of organizational climate dimensions, researchers analyzed organizational climate using several dimensions. Litwin and Stringer (1968), identified 6 dimensions for organizational

Climate: Reward outstanding performance, the degree of warmth felt by the staff with each other, sense of responsibility, encouraging risk-taking, sense of objective criteria to evaluate the performance, sense of belonging, the degree of support that an individual receives from his superiors at work.

Pritchard & Karasick, (1973) has identified 10 dimensions for organizational climate they are:-

- **Autonomy:** degree of freedom managers have in day-to-day operating decisions such as when to work, when not to work and how to solve job problems.
- **Conflict vs cooperation:** degree to which managers either compete with each other or work together in getting things done and in the allocation of scarce resources.
- **Social relations:** degree to which the organization has a friendly and warm social atmosphere.
- **Structure:** degree to which the organization specifies the methods and procedures used to accomplish tasks.
- **Level of rewards:** degree to which managers are well rewarded.
- **Performance-reward dependency:** extent to which the reward system is fair and appropriate.
- **Motivation to achieve:** degree to which the organization attempts to excel.
- **Status polarization:** degree to which there are definite physical distinction.
- **flexibility and innovation:** willingness to try new procedures and experiment with change which is not really necessary due to some potential crisis situation.
- **Decision centralization:** extent to which the organization delegates the responsibility for making decisions.
- **Supportiveness:** degree to which the organization is interested in and is willing to support its managers in both job- and non-job-related matters.

Koys & DeCotiis (1991) identified eight dimensions for organizational climate: autonomy, cohesion, trust, pressure, support, recognition, fairness and innovation. Hay group/McBer (1995), inspired by the work of Litwin and Stringer (1968), identified 6 dimensions of organizational climate that have consistently demonstrated a direct effect on individual and work-unit level performance (Watkin & Hubbard, 2003).

- **Flexibility:** the feeling employees have about constraints in the workplace; the degree to which they feel there are no unnecessary rules, procedures, policies, and practices that interfere with task accomplishment.
- **Responsibility:** the feeling that employees have that a lot of authority has been delegated to them.
- **Standards:** the emphasis that employees feel management puts on improving performance and doing one's best.
- **Rewards:** are the degree to which employees feel that they are being recognized and rewarded for good work.
- **Clarity:** the feeling that everyone knows what is expected of them and that they understand how those expectations relate to the larger goals and objectives of the organization.
- **Team Commitment:** the feeling that people are proud to belong to the organization and will provide extra effort when needed.

2.3 Creative behavior

There is a difference between creative behavior and innovation, Becheikh defined innovation as implemented technologically new products and processes and significant technological improvements in products and processes (Becheikh et al., 2006). The term incorporates the phenomenon of novelty and the possibility that its exploitation will create value (Johannssen, 2008). (Alzobi, 2015) defined creative behavior as a function of various decisions taken by individuals such as: realizing the status quo, gathering information about status quo, finding alternatives and evaluating them, experimenting these alternatives, and creative

behavior ends by rejecting or adopting particular idea. Creative behavior includes acts that lead to new ideas at any organizational level, its a distinctive behavior exercised by the individual in the workplace, also it is a behavior preceded innovation. (Alhawajreh & Shlash, 2012). Creative behavior containing several dimensions such as:

Opportunities discovery : a dimension that is interested in searching for creative opportunities intent to learn and benefit from them, which is necessary condition to move away from the existing red tape in the organization.

Verification: using scientific methods in ideas and solutions formulation and evaluate innovative ideas.

Challenge: by observing creative solutions and taking risks, where workers bear the primary responsibility to provide new ideas and persuade others. (Taled and Yahyaoui, 2015).

Application: It includes a follow-up creative opportunities, and to correct the deviations that appears.

Alomyan (2008) has indicated that the dimensions of the creative behavior include:

Originality: that the person with a creative original thought don't repeat thoughts of those around him.

Sensitivity to the problems: means that creative person can be aware of crises and problems in different situations better than anyone else.

Flexibility: means the person ability to convert direction of his thinking in the treatment of the problem from situation to another, and the person ability to quickly adapt to new developments and situations.

Ability to analyze: the mental capacity to analyze alternatives and trade-offs between them.

Fluency: means the ability to produce a large number of ideas in a given unit of time.

2.4 Innovation concept

Innovation is never a one-time phenomenon, but a long and cumulative process of a great number of organizational decision-making process, ranging from the phase of generation of a new idea to its implementation phase. New idea refers to the perception of a new customer need or a new way to produce.

(Afuah, 1998) classifies innovations according to technological, market, and organizational characteristics. Technological innovation is the knowledge of components, linkages between components, methods, processes and techniques that go into a product or service. It can be a product, a process, or a service. Product or service innovations should be new products or services aiming at satisfying some market needs. Process innovation is concerned with introducing new elements into an organization's operations such as input materials, task specifications, work and information flow mechanisms, and equipment used to produce a product or render a service.

Market innovation refers to the new knowledge embodied in distribution channels, product, applications, as well as customer expectations, preferences, needs, and wants. The main idea is the improvement of the components of the marketing-mix, that is, product, price, promotion and place. Administrative innovation involves innovations that pertain to the organizational structure and administrative processes. In this case it can be specifically related to strategies, structure, systems, or people in the organization (Popadiuk & Choo, 2006).

(Oconnor et al., 2004) classifies innovations to radical and incremental innovations, radical innovations are fundamental changes that represent revolutionary changes in technology. They represent clear departures from existing practice. Radical innovation is a major change that represents a new technological paradigm.

Radical change creates a high degree of uncertainty in organizations and industry. It also sweeps away significant parts of previous investments in technical skills and knowledge, designs, production techniques, plants and equipment. The change is not necessarily delimited by the supply side. It comes from a change on the demand side and in the organizational or institutional structure.

Incremental innovations are other changes in products and processes like changes which are insignificant, or do not involve a sufficient degree of novelty. Novelty refers to the aesthetic or other subjective qualities of the product. Time frame for incremental innovation less than radical innovation. Typically, Development structure in incremental innovation is a cross-functional team operates within an existing business unit whereas development structure in incremental innovation tends to originate in R&D.

2.5 Conceptual models

The study of (Samuel et al, 2015) aimed at identifying the effect of Creative climate on organizational resilience, in addition to explore the mediating role of innovation for (52) Governmental organization in Uganda, the study sample consisted of (242) Executives. The study showed that there is statistical significance impact for Creative climate on organizational resilience. Innovation mediates the relation between Creative climate and organizational resilience.

The study of (Gurpreet & Kuldeep, 2015) aimed at exploring the effect of organizational climate on Organizational Citizenship Behavior, as well as analyzing the effect of (17) factors consist organizational climate on Organizational Citizenship behavior at (75) Indian big organization working in food manufacturing industry. The study showed that there is statistical significance impact for Creative climate on Organizational Citizenship behavior., and that there is statistical significance impact for most Creative climate dimensions on Organizational Citizenship behavior, while there is no statistical significance impact for (efficiency, reflexivity and external focus) on Organizational Citizenship.

The study of (Alarabi, 2015) aimed at exploring the relation of organizational climate and administrative innovation at Saudi sport clubs. The study showed that there is statistical significance relation between organizational climate and administrative innovation. Also the averages of estimates of study sample towards the organizational climate and administrative innovation is high.

The study of (Alzobi, 2015) aimed at exploring impact of organizational climate dimensions (leadership style, organizational structure, technology and external environment) on creative behavior at Jordanian ministries. The study showed that there is

statistical significance relation between organizational climate and creative behavior. Also there is a difference in the averages of estimates of study sample towards the organizational climate due to functional variables.

The study of (Taled & Yahyaoui, 2015) aimed to determine the effect of empowerment strategy in developing creative behavior for Intellectual capital in the Algerian Saidal Foundation. The study reveals that the level of empowerment strategy and creative behavior is moderate, and there is positive relation between empowerment strategy and creative behavior.

The study of(Banoura, 2014) aimed at exploring the relation of organizational climate and administrative innovation at Palestine sport clubs, and exploring the differences in the averages of estimates of study sample towards the organizational climate due to demographic variables (experience, scientific qualification and specialization). The study showed that the level of organizational climate is moderate, and the level of administrative innovation is high. Also there is a difference in the averages of estimates of study sample towards the organizational climate due to experience and specialization.

The study of (Abdul Rahman, 2014) aimed at exploring the level of organizational climate dimensions (leadership styles, patterns of communication, participation in decision-making, technology, incentives system, and attention to workers) at Aplaqa applied university. And its relation with functional variables (managerial level and experience years). The study showed that the level of organizational climate is moderate . Also there is a difference in the averages of estimates of study sample towards the organizational climate due to managerial level.

The study of (Alzobi, 2013) aimed at exploring impact of organizational climate dimensions (leadership, organizational structure, control, motivation, and communication) on creative behavior at Orange Company in Jordan. The study showed that there is statistical significance impact for organizational climate dimensions (leadership, control, motivation, and communication) on creative behavior. Also there is a difference in the averages of estimates of study sample towards the organizational climate due to age and educational level .

The study of (Solmaz & Indra,2013) aimed at exploring impact of organizational climate dimensions on creative behavior at Malaysian SME working at service and manufacturing industries. . The study showed that there is statistical significance impact for organizational climate and creative behavior. And organizational climate dimensions (resources availability, mission clarity, and leaders support) were the strongest influence on creative behavior

The study of (Alsaudi,2012) aimed at exploring impact of organizational climate dimensions(Organizational structure, rules and regulations, participation, incentives, mode of communication and technology) on creative behavior dimensions at Jordanian private universities. The study showed that there is statistical significance impact for organizational climate dimensions on creative behavior dimensions. Also the level of awareness of employees about organizational climate dimensions is average, and the level of awareness of employees about creative behavior dimensions is high.

The study of (Gabor et al,2012) aimed at exploring impact of Creative organizational climate on creative behavior at Medical equipment industry in Hungary. In addition exploring the level of Creative organizational climate and the level of creative behavior the study showed that there is statistical significance impact for organizational climate dimensions on creative behavior dimensions. Also Creative organizational climate explain (42%) from variance in the dependent variable creative behavior.

The study of (Atheer, 2012) aimed at investigating the impact of organizational climate dimensions(Organizational structure, leadership, rewards, decision-making, communication, teamwork, and responsibility) on administrative innovation at General Company for the pharmaceutical industry in the province of Nineveh. Regression analyses showed that there is a significant relation between organizational climate dimensions and administrative innovation.

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The study of (Jon et al., 2011) aimed at investigating the impact of organizational climate on creative behavior in the Norwegian Service Sector, The study showed that Encouragement and support of new ideas were positively related to innovation, whereas holding on to established ways of performing work was negatively related to innovation. Also there is a difference in the averages of estimates of study sample towards the organizational climate due to gender and scientific qualification.

The study of (Rabia et al., 2010) aimed at exploring impact of organizational climate on creative behavior in a group of companies engaged in the distribution of consumer goods in Pakistan. The study sample consisted of (320) director, organizational climate has been measuring based on competing values model (goals model and system model). The results of multiple regression showed that there is statistical significance impact for organizational climate on creative behavior.

The study of (Lars, 2010) aimed at exploring the relationship between organizational climate and organizational performance for a large multinational company, and exploring the impact of management support and organizational unit size on organizational climate. Regression analyses showed that there is a significant relation between organizational climate and profitability, sustainability & growth, EBIT margin, productivity and employee engagement.

Furthermore, it was found that organizational climate is strongly influenced by management support, and that the relation between organizational unit size and organizational climate is mediated by management support.

The study of (Meriam, 2005) aimed at exploring the effect of Creative climate and learning organization on innovation, in addition comparing arithmetic means for Creative climate , learning organization and innovation due to occupational level within group of Indian private organizations award ISO certification. The study showed that Creative climate and learning organization explain (58.5%) from variance in the dependent variable innovation , and there is no statistical differences in the averages of estimates of study sample towards the organizational climate, learning organization, and creativity due to occupational level.

3. Method of the study

3.1 Study Community and Sample

The community of the study consists all workers and managers who are employed in (20) pharmaceutical industrial Jordanian companies. A simple-random sample was chosen from the study community, the researcher distributed (480) questionnaires, with due regard to employees at all levels. (457) questionnaires were received with the rate of return (95%). Only (12) questionnaires were dismissed because of being unusable for statistical analysis.

3.2 Study instrument

The researcher reviewed the theoretical background and previous studies about organizational climate and creative behavior. The researcher also reviewed many questionnaires that used in the previous studies ,so he designed one that reflects organizational climate and creative behavior. The parts of the questionnaire are:-

A- **Part one-** background information: - In this part, respondents were asked to indicate their gender, age, level of education, job title, and experience.

B-**Part two-** dimensions of the study:-This part covers dimensions:-

The first dimension –independent variable- organizational climate which contains (35) items. organizational climate contain the secondary dimensions:- items from (H1 to H7) related to flexibility, items from(H7 to H14) related to responsibility, items from (H15 to H21) related to rewards, items from(H22 to H28) related to clarity. and items from(H29 to H35) related to team commitment.

- **The second dimension-** dependent variable- is creative behavior which contains eight items from (H36 to H43).

The participants were asked to identify the degree of their agreement with each item in the second and third sections of the study , using five point Likert scale (5= strongly agree, 4= agree, 3=neutral, 2= disagree, and 1= strongly disagree). The scale was calculated through the following formula:

The highest point of the scale (5) – the lowest point of the scale (1)/ the number of required categories (3) = 1.33. Thus, 1.33 was added to the end of each category, so that the categories and the degree of agreement became as follows (from -1.00 to less than 2.33 = low) and (from 2.33 to 3.66 medium) and (from 3.67 to 5.00 = high).

3.3 Study Validity and Reliability

- Face validity: this is applied in the present study in two phases: First, the questionnaire sent to a pilot sample of (25) workers from different managerial level to assess the clarity of the questionnaire .Second, The questionnaire was reviewed by (14) referees from among the faculty members at Jordanian universities, and some items were adjusted based on their recommendations.

- Instrument reliability:- the current applied Cronbach's Alpha measures the reliability of measurement in similar research. Cronbach's Alpha coefficient value of all dimensions of the study is (93%).

3.4 Statistical methods used

In order to answer the questions of the study and test its hypotheses , the following statistics were employed: percentages , frequencies , One Way ANOVA, multiple regression, and (T- test).

3.5 Data Presentation and Analysis:

-A profile of the sample

The characteristics of the respondents are shown in table (1)

Table (1) Frequencies and Percentages of Demographics factors of the sample

Variable	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	262	58.9%
	Female	183	41.1%
Age	20-less than 30 Years	92	20.7%
	30- less than 40 Years	200	44.9%
	40- less than 50 Years	111	24.9%
	50- less than 60 Years	24	5.4%
	60+	18	4.1%
Education	Higher School	53	11.9%
	Diploma	65	14.6%
	Bachelor	260	58.4%
	Post Graduate	67	15.1%
Job Title	General Manger	21	4.7%
	Department Manager	28	6.2%
	Section Head	39	8.8%
	Supervisor	96	21.6%
	Worker	261	58.7%
Experience Years	Less Than 5 Years	61	13.7%
	6-10 Years	205	46.1%

	11-15 Years	91	20.4%
	More than 15 Years	88	19.8%

3.6 Analysis of the questions of the study:

-What is the level of Organizational climate and Organizational climate dimensions (responsibility, commitment to teamwork, rewards, flexibility, and clarity) and the level of employees creative behavior in the pharmaceutical industry?.

Table 2: means and standard deviations of the level of Organizational climate and creative behavior

Rank	dimension	mean	Standard deviation	Degree of assessment
2	flexibility	3.57	.49	moderate
5	responsibility	3.53	.39	moderate
4	rewards	3.54	.50	moderate
1	Goals clarity	3.61	.39	moderate
3	Team commitment	3.55	.48	moderate
Organizational climate as a whole		3.54	.41	moderate
Creative behavior		3.58	.40	moderate

Table (2) shows the level of Organizational climate among members of study sample at Jordanian pharmaceutical companies was moderate, with a mean of (3.54) and a standard deviation of (0.41) , which suggests the similarity of the responses of the participants of the study concerning Organizational climate.

Table (2) shows also that the means of the responses of the participants of the study concerning Organizational climate dimensions ranged between (3.53- 3.61), the highest being for the dimension of goal clarity, with a mean of (3.61) and a standard deviation of (0.39) and a moderate degree of assessment, and lastly came the dimension of responsibility with a mean of (3.53) with a mean and a standard deviation of (0.39) and a moderate degree of assessment.

3.7 Study Hypothesis Testing

The first main hypothesis : there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for Organizational climate on employees creative behavior. Simple linear regression was employed as illustrated in tables 4 and 5

Table 3 : results of simple linear regression for the main hypothesis

model	Source of variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean of squares	R	R ²	Adjusted R	F value	significance
Simple regression	Regression	46.019	1	46.019	.788	.621	.620	725.342	.000(a)
	Residual	28.106	443	.063					
	Total	74.126	444						

the table above shows that the value of (f) is (725.342) , with a statistical significance of (0.000), which is less than ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), which indicates the interpretive and predictive power for using the simple linear regression model between the independent variable (Organizational climate) and the dependent variable (creative behavior) thus, the simple linear regression model is appropriate for the assessment of the causative relationship between the independent variable (Organizational climate) and the dependent variable (creative behavior). It is also shown that the value of the correlation coefficient between independent variable (Organizational climate) and the dependent variable(creative behavior) was (.788), and that the value of (R²) was (.621), and the value of adjusted (R²) was (.620)

which indicates that the independent variable (Organizational climate) was able to account for (62%) of dependent variable(creative behavior),and the rest is due to other factors. the changes which occurred to the

Table 4 the significance of standardized and unstandardized simple linear regression coefficient of the first hypotheses

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.792	.104		7.585	.000
Organizational climate	.788	.029	.788	26.932	.000

Table (4) shows that:-

- the presence of a statistical significance for the constant of the simple linear regression formula , (t) value was (7.585) and with a statistical significance of (0.000) which less than ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) which indicates the significance of the constant of the simple linear regression model whose value was (.792).
- the presence of a statistical significance for the standardized and unstandardized simple linear regression formula related to the independent variable (Organizational climate) in which the value of (t), was (26.932), with a significance of (0.000) which is less than the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), which indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis , and accepting the

alternative hypothesis which states there is statistically significant effect at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for Organizational climate on employees creative behavior.

The Second main hypothesis : there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for Organizational climate dimensions (flexibility, responsibility, rewards, clarity and team commitment) on employees creative behavior. Multiple linear regression was used in exploring the presence of a statistically significant effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). Upon inserting the independent variables into the multiple linear regression analysis (flexibility, responsibility, rewards, Goal clarity, and Team commitment) through stepwise method. Table (5) shows that all organizational climate dimensions has a predictive power and is statistically significant.

Table 5 : multiple linear regression for the first hypothesis

Independent variables	Source of variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean of squares	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F value	significance
responsibility	Regression	52.536	1	52.536	.842	.709	.708	1077.982	.000(a)
	Residual	21.590	443	.049					
	Total	74.126	444						
Team commitment	Regression	57.980	2	28.990	.884	.782	.781	793.608	.000(b)
	Residual	16.146	442	.037					
	Total	74.126	444						
Reward	Regression	63.474	3	21.158	.925	.856	.855	875.978	.000(c)
	Residual	10.652	441	.024					
	Total	74.126	444						
Clarity	Regression	64.582	4	16.146	.933	.871	.870	744.396	000(d)
	Residual	9.543	440	.022					
	Total	74.126	444						
Flexibility	Regression	65.575	5	13.115	.941	.885	.883	673.363	.000(e)
	Residual	8.550	439	.019					
	Total	74.126	444						

Table (5) shows that the value of (f) is (673.363) with a statistical significance of (0.000), which is less than ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), which indicates the significance and predictive power of the multiple linear regression, between Organizational climate dimensions (flexibility, responsibility, rewards, clarity and team commitment) and the dependent variable (employees creative behavior.). Thus, the multiple linear regression model suitable for the assessment of causative relationship between the independent variables Organizational climate dimensions (flexibility, responsibility, rewards, clarity and team commitment) and the dependent variable (employees creative behavior.)

Table (5) shows that all independent variables had statistically significant effects on creative behavior, responsibility influence came first concerning the size of the effect, and its multiple correlation coefficient value was (.842) and the (R²) was (.709) and the value of Adjusted (R²) was (.708) which indicates that the responsibility was capable of accounting for (70.8%) of the changes in the dependent variable (creative behavior). Team commitment came second in terms of the size of the effect, and its multiple correlation coefficient when added to the effect of responsibility was (.884), (R²) was (.782) for both dimensions, and the value of their Adjusted R² was (.781) which indicates that the dimensions of responsibility and team commitment together accounted for (78.1%) of the changes in the dependent variable (creative behavior).

Reward came third in terms of the size of the effect, and its multiple correlation coefficient when added to the effect of responsibility and team commitment was (.925), (R²) was (.856) for both dimensions, and the value of their Adjusted R² was (.855) which indicates that the dimensions of responsibility, team commitment and reward together accounted for (85.5%) of the changes in the dependent variable (creative behavior).

Clarity came forth in terms of the size of the effect, and its multiple correlation coefficient when added to the effect of responsibility, team commitment and reward was (.933), (R²) was (.871) for all dimensions, and the value of their Adjusted (R²) was (.870) which indicates that the dimensions of responsibility, team commitment and reward together accounted for (85.5%) of the changes in the dependent variable (creative behavior).

Flexibility came fifth in terms of the size of the effect, and its multiple correlation coefficient when added to the effect of responsibility, team commitment, reward and clarity was (.941), (R²) was (.885) for all dimensions, and the value of their Adjusted (R²) was (.883) which indicates that the dimensions of responsibility, team commitment, reward, clarity and flexibility together accounted for (88.3%) of the changes in the dependent variable (creative behavior).

Table 6: the significance of standardized and unstandardized multiple linear regression coefficient of the first hypotheses

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.284	.067		4.237	.000
responsibility	.736	.021	.890	35.084	.000
Team commitment	.687	.029	.814	23.538	.000
rewards	.448	.037	.551	12.076	.000
Goal clarity	.175	.020	.170	8.658	.000
Flexibility	.230	.032	.277	7.140	.000

The table(6) shows:-

- The existence of a statistical significance for the constant of the multiple linear regression formula, in which the value of(t) was (4.237) with a statistical significance of (0.000) which is below the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), which indicates the significance of the constant (.284).
- The presence of a statistical significance for the coefficient of the multiple linear regression formula related to the independent variable responsibility , for which the value of t was (35.084) , with a statistical significance of (0.000) , which is below the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) , which suggests the rejection of the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis which states that : There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for responsibility on employees creative behavior.
- The presence of a statistical significance for the coefficient of the multiple linear regression formula related to the independent variable team commitment , for which the value of t was (23.538) , with a statistical significance of (0.000) , which is below the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) , which suggests the rejection of the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis which states that : There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for team commitment on employees creative behavior.
- The presence of a statistical significance for the coefficient of the multiple linear regression formula related to the independent variable reward , for which the value of t was (12.076) , with a statistical significance of (0.000) , which is below the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) , which suggests the rejection of the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis which states that : There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for reward on employees creative behavior.
- The presence of a statistical significance for the coefficient of the multiple linear regression formula related to the independent variable goal clarity , for which the value of t was (8.658) , with a statistical significance of (0.000) , which is below the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) , which suggests the rejection of the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis which states that : There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for goal clarity on employees creative behavior.
- The presence of a statistical significance for the coefficient of the multiple linear regression formula related to the independent variable flexibility , for which the value of t was (7.140) , with a statistical significance of (0.000) , which is below the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) , which suggests the rejection of the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis which states that : There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for flexibility on employees creative behavior.

The Third main hypothesis : there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of demographic factors(gender, age, educational level, experience, job title) at organizational climate.

Sub hypothesis: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of gender on workers perception towards organizational climate. To test the sub hypothesis, we used (T- test) for independent – samples.

Table7:Independent Samples T- test of gender

	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	Sig(2- tailed)
male	3.55	.37	433	.211	.833
female	3.54	.44			

Table (7) indicates that the mean for male responses for organizational climate was (3.55) and the mean for female responses for organizational climate was (3.54). Besides, the Sig(2- tailed) is (.833) for organizational climate, so we accept the null hypotheses that there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of gender on workers perception towards organizational climate.

Sub hypothesis: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of age on workers perception towards organizational climate.

Sub hypothesis: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of educational level on workers perception towards organizational climate.

Sub hypothesis: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of experience on workers perception towards

organizational climate.

Sub hypothesis: there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of job title on workers perception towards organizational climate. To test the sub hypothesis, we used One – Way ANOVA test.

Table (8) One – Way ANOVA test of the impact of age, educational level, experience and job title

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
age	Between groups	.583	4	.146	.872	.481
	With in groups	73.568	440	.167		
	Total	74.152	444			
educational level	Between groups	1.113	3	.371	2.240	.083
	With in groups	73.038	441	.166		
	Total	74.152	444			
experience	Between groups	1.052	3	.371	2.215	.098
	With in groups	73.100	441	.166		
	Total	74.152	444			
job title	Between groups	1.290	3	.371	1.947	.102
	With in groups	72.862	441	.322		
	Total		444			

Table (8) indicates that:

- There aren't differences among groups according to their age. Besides, the Sig is (.481), so we accept the null hypotheses that there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of age on workers perception towards organizational climate.
- There aren't differences among groups according to their educational level. Besides, the Sig is (.083), so we accept the null hypotheses that there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of educational level on workers perception towards organizational climate.
- There aren't differences among groups according to their age. Besides, the Sig is (.098), so we accept the null hypotheses that there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of experience on workers perception towards organizational climate.
- There aren't differences among groups according to their age. Besides, the Sig is (.102), so we accept the null hypotheses that there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of job title on workers perception towards organizational climate.

4. Results and conclusions:-

1-The results related to the first question What is the level of Organizational climate, Organizational climate dimensions (responsibility, and a commitment to teamwork, rewards, flexibility, and clarity) in the pharmaceutical industry?

Table (2) shows that the level of Organizational climate as a whole at Jordanian pharmaceutical companies is moderate with a mean of (3.54) and a standard deviation (0.41). Based on this result, the researcher believes that there is awareness at the Jordanian pharmaceutical companies of the importance of Organizational climate, also it is provide suitable climates for Creative behavior. Practicing the dimensions of Organizational climate was as follows:

The dimension of goals clarity was ranked first, with a mean of (3.61) and a moderate degree of significance. The dimension of flexibility came next, with a mean of (3.57), and a standard deviation of (0.39) and a medium degree of assessment. The dimension of Team commitment has the third rank, with a mean of (3.55) and a standard deviation of (0.48) and a medium degree of assessment. The dimension of rewards was ranked fourth with a mean of (3.54) and standard deviation of (0.50) and a medium degree of assessment. The dimension of responsibility was ranked fifth with a mean of (3.53) and standard deviation of (0.49) and a medium degree of assessment. This show that the Jordanian pharmaceutical companies are aware of the importance of providing healthy climate because it affects the performance of employees, and contributing in goals achievement. This result is consistent with studies of (Alsaudi, 2012) , study of (Taled & Yahyaoui, 2015), and the study of (Banoura, 2014).

2- The results related to the second question What is the level of employees creative behavior in the pharmaceutical industry?.

Table (2) shows the level of Creative behavior among members of study sample at Jordanian pharmaceutical companies was moderate, with a mean of (3.58) and a standard deviation of (0.40) , which suggests the similarity of the responses of the participants of the study concerning Creative behavior.

Based on this result, Creative behavior includes acts that lead to new ideas at any organizational level and a special conduct exercised by the individual in the workplace. Also, providing any new idea for a new pharmaceutical product, do not come easily, because of the sensitivity of the product, and the difficulty of access to local and international approvals to produce a new drug.

The results related to the main hypotheses:

- The results related to the first hypothesis shows that their is statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for Organizational climate on employees creative behavior. Through the results of simple linear regression, it was shown that Organizational climate account for (62%) of the changes which occurred to the dependent variable (creative behavior creative behavior), and the rest is due to other factors. Based on this result, the researcher believes that Jordanian pharmaceutical companies should invest innovative new ideas, working to turn them into useful products, and providing technical capabilities that relate to inventions and product

protection and intellectual property. This result is consistent with studies of (Alzobi, 2015) , the study of (Alarabi, 2015), and the study of (Samuel et al., 2015).

-The results related to the second hypothesis shows that there is statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for Organizational climate dimensions (flexibility, responsibility, rewards, clarity and team commitment) on employees creative behavior. Through the results of multiple linear regression, it was shown that the dimensions of flexibility, responsibility, rewards, clarity and team commitment together accounted for (70.82%) of the changes in the dependent variable (creative behavior). Based on this result, the researcher believes that organizational climate has great importance, because of its direct impact on all organizational processes, functions and effectiveness. Besides, it influence the work of the Organization, and its relationship with the external environment. Positive organizational climate create a favorable environment for innovation through the cooperation of workers to find new ways to accomplish tasks.

- The results related to the third hypothesis shows that there is no statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of demographic factors (gender, age, educational level, experience, job title) at organizational climate. Based on this result, the researcher believes that the employees are similar aware of organizational climate, regardless of their demographic factors.. This result is consistent with a study (Meriam, 2015) and the study of (al-Astal, 2011).

5. Recommendations:

Based on the results of the study, the study recommends:

- 1- Providing a suitable work environment to increase the creative behavior of employees, In light of increasing foreign competition and the challenges of technical development.
- 2- Jordanian pharmaceutical companies should Provide a suitable climate for creative behavior and generate new styles for their products and services, because its beneficial and increase its market share and competitiveness.
- 3-The pharmaceutical industrial organizations should focus on participation in strategic planning, and clarify the mission and goals of their organizations for workers, besides, taking the risk to exploit market opportunities.
- 4- Encouraging managers and top level of management to delegate their routine duties and using participation in their work and decisions.
- 5- Focusing on knowledge sharing through empowerment of employees and providing them with necessary skills that are consistent with the current requirements of the era, knowledge is a tool stimulate creative behavior.

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